

MĀLAVIKĀGNIMITRAM: A CRITICAL STUDY WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO DRAMATURGY

Annotation:

Kālidāsa's early dramatic work, Mālavikāgnimitram, stands out in the Sanskrit play tradition. Unlike his more known plays such as Abhijñānaśākuntalam and Vikramorvaśīyam, this work depicts a somewhat lighter theme of courtly love, intrigue, and royal life. The plot follows King Agnimitra's love for the maid Mālavikā, placed in the socio-political and cultural context of the Śuṅga dynasty.

Mālavikāgnimitram teaches dramatists how to apply the concepts of Bharata Muni's Nāṭyaśāstra in practice. The play exemplifies Sanskrit drama's structural structure by dividing it into acts (aṅkas), using dramatic junctures (sandhi), and using features like viṣkambhaka, praveśaka, and nāndī. The use of Śṛṅgāra rasa (the aesthetic sentiment of love) is effectively linked with aspects of humor (hāsyā) and mild tension, resulting in dramatic balance and audience engagement.

The play's hero, King Agnimitra, is portrayed as a dhīralalita type with grace and amorous tendencies, reflecting classical rules in portrayal. Mālavikā, the heroine, has charm, modesty, and emotional depth, reflecting traditional aesthetic values. Supporting characters, such as the queen and attendants, add to the dramatic dimension and help the plot expand through dialogue and situational development.

The play also demonstrates the excellent use of stage customs, music, and dancing, emphasizing the performative part of Sanskrit dramaturgy. Kālidāsa's use of lyrical passages and dramatic dialogue showcases his creative talent and ability to balance literary beauty with theatrical viability. Examining Mālavikāgnimitram from a dramaturgy perspective enhances our comprehension of Kālidāsa's dramatic art and demonstrates how classical theoretical frameworks were imaginatively transformed in practical dramatic composition.

Keywords:

Kālidāsa, Mālavikāgnimitram, Sanskrit Drama, Dramaturgy, Śṛṅgāra Rasa, Nāyaka-Nāyikā, Sandhi (dramatic structure).

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Introduction:

Kālidāsa is one of the best Sanskrit dramatists and, after *Aśvaghoṣa*, one of the most famous names in Sanskrit literature in Indian literary history. *Kālidāsa* was a well-known Classical Sanskrit playwright

who is often regarded as the best poet and dramatist in the Sanskrit language. *Kālidāsa* is the best person to speak for the New World's heart. In a nutshell, Asia is the world's heart; India is the heart of Asia and *Kālidāsa* is the heart of India. Nothing is known about *Kālidāsa*'s life. In his writings, the poet has kept a deliberate quiet regarding himself.

Regarding *Kālidāsa*'s works, it is well known that he created seven works, viz. 1. *Kumārsambhava* and 2. *Raghuvamśa* (both are the *Mahākāvya*s) 3. *Rtusamhāra*, (*giṭī kāvya*) 4. *Meghadūta* (a *Khaṇḍakāvya*) 5. *Mālavikāgnimitra*, 6. *Vikramorvaśīya* and 7. *Abhijñāna Śakuntala* (three dramas). *Kāvya* is in the first four and drama is in the last three. The first play written by the great poet *Kālidāsa* is *Mālavikāgnimitra*. This beautiful plot play entices readers and keeps them glued to the page until the very end. The play's plot is cleverly constructed, and it centres on the King's love interest, who is a royal palace maid. The development of love plots and numerous incidents that propel the story forward are commendable and beautifully described, while remaining true to the central theme.

Critical Study with Special Reference to Dramaturgy:

The playwright has successfully linked the various situations that result from a hidden motive. We have to say that *Kālidāsa* has handled the intrigue in a very well-thought-out manner. And he's kept the majority of the information to himself. Even the plot of the *Vidūṣaka* is revealed only as the dramatic events unfold. As a result, the mystery and suspense are maintained throughout the drama, and it never loses its appeal. *Mālavikāgnimitra* by *Kālidāsa* is considered to be one of the best love-intrigue plays in Sanskrit drama. *Kālidāsa* has done an excellent job with the play, and his handling of the intriguing and plot-motivating secrets has made this 'intrigue' much more charming than any other.

There are huge numbers of characters in *Kālidāsa*'s play '*Mālavikāgnimitra*'. Out of 36 characters, 25 characters appear on the stage whereas; the names of the 11 characters are mentioned. They do not appear on the stage. There are altogether 19 male characters and 17 female characters. Thus the ratio of the character distribution is almost equal. Playwrights like *Kālidāsa* could only handle such a huge number of characters in their plays. The characters are portrayed very rationally in his masterpiece named '*Mālavikāgnimitra*' of *Kālidāsa*. For the principal characters of the play, the author stands important among other Indian dramatists. He shows his skill in describing the character throughout the whole drama. Regarding male characters of *Mālavikāgnimitra*, *Agnimitra* is the hero, the King of *Vidiśā* and he is *Dhīralalita* type. At the very outset of the play *Mālavikāgnimitra*, *sūtradhāra* physically appears on the stage and reads the prologue. It is very important to say that *Vidūṣaka*'s character is used by *kālidāsa* for accomplishing the ultimate goal of king *Agnimitra*. The character of *Gautama* i.e. *vidūṣaka* is very vital in this play *Mālavikāgnimitra* in comparison to that of the other plays of *Kālidāsa*. *Goutama* possesses a sense of humour that works as comic relief for the audience. Only because of *vidūṣaka* the union of *Mālavikā* and *Agnimitra* was possible. Other minor male characters viz. *Sūtradhāra*, *Pāripārśika*, *Amātya*, *Haradatta*, *Gaṇadāsa*, *Kouñcukī*, *Sārasika*, and *Vaitālika* plays different categories with different positions. On the other hand the heroine of the play i.e. *Mālavikā* falls under the category of *kaṇyā* type *nāyikā*. In *Mālavikā*, the poet has created a model of a lovely, pure-minded, and accomplished young lady. She was born a princess and is the sister of *Mādhavsena*, the *Vidarbha* Kingdom's prince. The character of *Dhāriṇī* is the king *Agnimitra*'s chief queen, a significant female character in the play *Mālavikāgnimitra*. Even though the fact that she is not the play's heroine, she appears to be the story's controlling force. *Dhāriṇī*'s character is a perfect representation of an ideal Indian woman. Again the character of *Irāvati*, King *Agnimitra*'s second wife, has been described by *Kālidāsa* as a proud, jealous, and quarrelsome lady. Her physical appearance in the play is somewhat different and strange. Besides this the other minor female characters viz. *Parivrājikā*, *Pratīhārī*, *Bakulāvalikā*, *Koumudikā*, *Nāgarikā*, *Nipuṇikā*, *Samāhitikā*, *Madhukarikā*, *Jyotsnikā*, and *Madanikā* plays different categories with different positions.

Sanskrit literature is thought to be the world's oldest literature. Sanskrit poetics is the apex of theories and laws relating to poetry and drama in India. Sanskrit poetics, like Aristotle's Poetics, is concerned with drama. The *Nāṭyaśāstra* of *Bharata* is a landmark in ancient Sanskrit literature. *Mahākavi*

Kālidāsa holds a special place in both Sanskrit and world literature. Some well-known dramatists are *Bhāsa*, *Bhavbhuti*, *Harsa*, *Śūdraka*, and *Aśvaghosha*.

Drama is one of the ancient forms of literature as well as the pleasure history of mankind. Man has found pleasure in emulating others and in this virtual reality world that he has created since the ancient period. According to encyclopedia Britannica, “Drama, a poem containing some certain action, and representing a true picture of human life, for the delight and improvement of mankind”. On the one hand, the trend of emulating and creating another universe inspired him to create dramas, and on the other, to build a formula for writing and acting. There is a rich literary tradition of drama (theatrical literature) and dramaturgy in India as well (discussion of the structure and practical application of drama). It all starts with *Bharata’s Nāṭyaśāstra*, which narrates how *Brahmā* taught the fifth Veda to the sage *Bharata*. *Bharata* also relates how the first-ever drama was performed in front of the gods in this composition.

Dramas have been composed and dramaturgy guidelines have been developed throughout history. Many of these pieces have not survived, but a significant number have, giving us more than a sense of ancient Indian dramaturgy. Using *Bharata’s* masterwork as a foundation, *Bhaṭṭa Lollaṭa*, *Śaṅkuka*, *Bhaṭṭanāyaka*, *Abhinavagupta*, *Abhinavabhāratī*, *Rāmachandra*, and *Gunachandra*, *Ruyyaka*, *Dhanañjaya*, *Sāradātanaya*, *Sārṅhadeva*, *Viśwanātha* explores many components of dramaturgy – a piece of contemporary evidence to Indian drama’s vitality and ever greenness. Not only is ancient drama an old art form, but it is also the source of all other fine arts like dancing, singing, sculpting, painting, and even architecture. The classification of drama and various technicalities such as *Purvaraṅga*, *Nāndī*, *Vṛtti*, *Prasthāvanā*, and its five types are discussed in this chapter. Because these are the important aspects of a drama, a clear discussion is required to justify the status of the drama. *Patākāsthānaka*, *Arthopakṣepeka*, the plot of the drama, five stages of action, five varieties of *Arthaprakṛti’s*, and five Sandhis along with their verities.

Sanskrit drama is termed *Drśyakāvya*. It is called *Rūpaka* as the *rūpa* of a character is imitated by an actor or actress on the stage. *Bharata* in his famous work *Nāṭyaśāstra* has introduced ten *Rūpakas*. His classification of dramas has been adopted by almost all the later theorists. *Bharata* has discussed all the ten *Rūpakas* in his work. After *Bharata*, *Dhanañjaya* and *Viśwanātha* have put their opinions regarding these ten *Rūpakas*. Though they have not attempted to modify anything of the ten *Rūpakas*, discussed by their authority, they further added some sub-divisions of *Uparūpakas*. *Bharata* has not discussed anything about *Uparūpakas* but while discussing the *Rūpakas* he mentioned a variety called *Nātikā*. According to *Viśwanātha*, *drśyakāvya* is of two type’s *Rūpaka* and *Uparūpaka* or minor *Rūpaka*. Where *Rūpaka* is divided into ten and *Uparūpaka* is divided into eighteen varieties. Every *Rūpaka* differs from each other in its characteristics such as the nature of the plot, the hero and the heroine, the sentiment and the length of the play, or the numbers of the act. Among the ten *Rūpakas*, *Nāṭaka* and *Prakaraṇa* are considered the more developed forms consisting of not less than five acts to represent the five stages of development of the plot.

For the attainment of the status of a perfect drama, it must possess certain dramaturgical laws. If a drama follows the dramaturgical cannon then only it can be termed a perfect drama. *Kālidāsa* has used the dramaturgical prescription in his all plays. In following dramaturgical law, he has used elements like *Nāndī*, *Prastāvana* presented by *sūtradhāra* and eventually used the *Bharatavākya*. To show the development of the story, *Kālidāsa* employed five types of *Artaprakṛiti*, five types of *Kāryavasthā*, and five types of *Sandhi*. Moreover, he has used other necessary dramaturgical prescriptions such as *svgata*, *prakāśa*, *janāntika*, *apavārita*, etc. with extreme excellence. Consequently, it is to be said that *Kālidāsa* has followed all the dramaturgical laws very beautifully in all his plays from the perspective of *Nāṭyaśāstra*.

When it comes to *Kālidāsa’s* plays, we notice that, while the blessing of Lord *Śiva* is sought in each of his three plays through the benedictory stanza, we don’t find *Nāndī* in the broad sense as we do in the plays of other playwrights. The *Nāndī* of *Mālavikāgnimitra* is made up of eight *Pāda’s*. The *Pāda* here

refers to a quarter of a verse. Because the *Mālavikāgnimitra*'s *Nāndī* is made up of two verses, *Pāda*'s are present to form an *Astapāda Nāndī*.

The *Prayogātīśaya* type of *Prastāvanā* has been introduced in this play of *Kālidāsa*. In this type of *Prastāvanā*, the stage manager directly indicates the character's entrance with the words "here enters so and so on". All three plays of *Kālidāsa* contain a direct indication of the character's entrance onto the stage. In *Mālavikāgnimitra*, *Kālidāsa* used *Prayogātīśaya* type *Prastāvanā*. One of the striking features of the *Prastāvanā* of *Mālavikāgnimitra* is that here the characters hurriedly enter the stage.

The dramatist introduces the *Viṣkambhaka* in the first act of the *Mālavikāgnimitra*, right after the *Prayogātīśaya* type of *Prastāvanā*. This *Viṣkambhaka* is called as *Miśra Viṣkambhaka*. Because the second-rate character *Gaṇadāsa* speaks Sanskrit and the two third-rate characters, *Kaumudikā* and *Bakulāvalikā* speak in *Prākṛt*.

The third-rate character alone takes part in the *Praveśaka*. The dramatist generally uses a *Praveśaka* to indicate the events which have occurred after the end of a certain action before the beginning of a new act. *Praveśaka* is an explanatory scene serving the same purpose as the *Viṣkambhaka*, only the difference is that the characters taking part in this scene are exclusive of the inferior class speaking the *Prākṛt* language. Beginning of the third and fifth acts of the play *Mālavikāgnimitra*, where the *Praveśaka* is discovered. In *Kālidāsa*'s *Mālavikāgnimitra*, *Cūlikā* has been used altogether five times. In the first Act of the play, the announcement of the fight between two dance teachers named *Gaṇadāsa* and *Haradutta* started too much bragging. Similarly in the second Act *Baitālika* inform the audience regarding the mid-day hours from behind the scene. Moreover, in the fourth act as well the use of *Cūlikā* is very much evident when the announcement of the blooming of the *Aśoka* tree has been presented from behind the scene. Similarly in the fifth act, the announcement of the defeat of king *Vidarbha* is presented from behind the stage, through the conversation of *Baitālika*. Towards the end of the first act of the play *Mālavikāgnimitra*, we get the example of *Aṅkāvatāra*. Here, the two dance teachers decided to show their excellency through their disciples. It's a scene in which the central theme of all acts is summed up in a single sentence. It is typically utilized in a play's first act. *Kālidāsa* didn't make use of *Aṅkamukha* in his first play *Mālavikāgnimitra*.

In *Kālidāsa*'s drama there are five types of *Arthaprakṛti* as described by Sanskrit rhetoricians. *Arthaprakṛti* denotes the stage of action. To create the orderly sequence of the incidents in the play *Arthaprakṛti* is used. In this play, the incident of beholding the picture of *Mālavikā* by the king is considered the *Bīja* of the entire drama. As the action proceeds, this minor incident takes a greater shape in the entire play and the things become more intense. In the first Act of the play through the conversations of two maid-servants, it is evident that one day queen *Dhāriṇī* visited the picture hall to see all the portraits present over there which are made by *Āchārya*. In the drama *Mālavikāgnimitra*, bellow mentioned incidents are termed as *Bindu*. Firstly, in the first Act of the play, we see that the King of *Vidharbha* presented certain conditions to the king *Agnimitra* through a letter. Soon after that incident, *Vidūṣaka* found a way through which the King can see *Mālavikā* physically whom he only saw in the painting. Thus, to fulfill the desire of the king, *Vidūṣaka* went to him and whispered something in his ear. Thus, the whole event of this scene became even more intense and descriptive in the latter parts. So, it is an example of *Bindu*. Secondly, the two dance teachers named *Gaṇadāsa* and *Haradutta* of queen *Dhāriṇī* wanted to prove their excellency through the dance presentation of their disciples. Here queen *Dhāriṇī* was seen to be very angry. Enraged queen *Dhāriṇī* moved her face away because she was not willing to see the performance. This event turned out to be more intense and elaborate in the latter part of the play. So, this event example of *Bindu*. Thirdly, in the second Act, after the departure of *Mālavikā* and *Gaṇadāsa* from the stage, the audience could see a break in the main plot of the story. However, later on, the king urged *Vidūṣaka* to find out several ways so that he could meet *Mālavikā*. Thus, with this scene, the story of the main plot started to grow in a detailed manner. The third element of the plot is the *Patākā*, it is an ornament of the dramatic plot and its use is recommended as often as possible in a drama. The entire incident of rescuing the *Nāgamudrā* in the

play *Mālavikāgnimitra* is a fine instance of *Patākā*. *Vidūṣaka* endeavors to release from prison through this *Nāgamudrā*. Although, the scene of *Nāgamudrā* is a trivial action in the play, but extremely helpful in accomplishing the main action of the play. *Prakarī* is a minor incident that takes up a small amount of the dramatic res-business. It also contributes to the main cause, but for a much shorter period than *Patākā*. *Prakarī*'s leader has no personal motivation to serve. In the play, *Mālavikāgnimitra*, when the real identity of *Mālavikā* is revealed as being the sister of King *Mādhava* can be seen as an example of *Prakarī* the play. In the fifth Act, a detailed description of the defeat of King *Jañjasena* is presented. When the two girls were accompanied by the messenger, they could easily identify *Mālavikā* and *Kauśikī*. This incident works positively for *Agnimitra* to accomplish the ultimate intention. So this is an example of *Prakarī*. The fifth element of the plot is the denouement, also known as the *Kārya*, which depicts the play's cause or motif. The ultimate union of the hero and heroine is considered *Kārya* in all three plays of *Kālidāsa*. As soon as the real identity of *Mālavikā* of being a princess is revealed, queen *Dhāriṇī* urges the King *Agnimitra* to accept *Mālavikā* as his wedded wife. Eventually, *Mālavikā* and *Agnimitra* tie the pious knot of marriage with one another. Thus, the eventual union of hero and heroine (*Mālavikā* and *Agnimitra*) is considered as *Kārya* of the play.

A *Sandhi* is the union of various phases of the main action with their subordinates. As a result, it is said to denote the component divisions of the dramatic action. The formation of dramatic junctures depends on the combination of the various stages of action (*Kāryavasthā*) with the respective sources of the plot (*Arthaprakṛti*) in the constitution of these *Sandhis*. In the first act of the play, *Kālidāsa* has put light into *Mukha-Sandhi*. Here from the beginning of the first act up to seeking *Vidūṣaka*'s permission from *Agnimitra* regarding his opinion comes under the part of *Mukha-Sandhi*. The attraction of the King toward *Mālavikā* when he sees her portrait in the First Act of the play sows the germ of love. This germ, in some places, is evident whereas, sometimes it tends to be disappeared. In the second Act, the *Bīja* is seen when King *Agnimitra* sees *Mālavikā*'s physical appearance through her dance performance. However, the *Bīja* disappears when *Mālavikā* departs along with the dance teacher after her performance. Thus, *Pratimukha-Sandhi* results from the *Bīja* that appears in certain scenes of the play, and sometimes it doesn't. *Garbha Sandhi* starts from the second Act of the play and continues up to the third Act. In the second Act, the *Bīja* (germ) tends to be disappeared with the departure of *Mālavikā*. Whereas, King *Agnimitra* requested *Vidūṣaka* some ways through which we can meet *Mālavikā*. In this scene, the *Bīja* appears once again. From the consolation of *Vidūṣaka*, the King gets a hope to meet *Mālavikā* but, queen *Dhāriṇī* works as an obstacle to that. Again in the third Act, a ray of hope is visible as both *Mālavikā* and *Agnimitra* yearn to have one another. However, the *Bīja* vanishes once again when *Irābatī* comes to *Pramadabana* and moves away out of anger. Consequently, the cycle of the *Bīja* being disappeared, attained, and searched goes on throughout the play. So it is an example of *Garbha-Sandhi*. The actions of certain minor helpers whose efforts of shorter duration known as incidents ensure the certainty of success put a premium on the prospect of success. The stage of *Niyatāpti*, combined with the element of *Prakarī*, creates the *Vimarśa-Sandhi*. In the fourth Act of the play, the evidence of *Vimarśa-Sandhi* is very much visible. Whereas the news of the blooming of the *Aśoka* tree before five days is also evident which paves the way for *Mālavikā* to ask for the desired result from queen *Dhāriṇī*. So it is an example of *Vimarśa-Sandhi*. At the very outset of the fifth Act, queen *Dhāriṇī* expresses her extreme happiness on hearing the news of bloomed *Aśoka* tree and invites the king for a grand celebration. Starting from this incident up to the end of this Act, all scenes are entitled to *Nirvahaṇa Sandhi*.

The dramatic action begins with the germ of the dramatic plot. This action aims to achieve a specific goal, which necessitates a strong desire to succeed. A drama's psychological phenomenon goes through five stages known as *Kāryāvastha*. In the first Act of the play *Mālavikāgnimitra*, from the conversation between *Vidūṣaka* and the king, it is evident that the king urges him to arrange some ways through which he can get *Mālavikā* forever. The king says *Vidūṣaka* to find out certain ways so that he can behold *Mālavikā* physically. *Vidūṣaka* obeys the king's order and repeats the words after

the king. This incident in the first Act of the play is a fine example of the *Ārambha* type of *Kāryāvastha*. At the outset of the second Act of the play *Mālavikāgnimitra*, *Vidūṣaka* endeavors to create a chance for the dance performance of the disciples of *Gaṇadāsa* so that, the King could easily see *Mālavikā*'s enchanting beauty via her dance. Here, the King asks *Parivrājikā*- '*Bhagavati!* Either *Gaṇadāsa* or *Haradutta*, who would perform first?' Responding to King's question and being the part of the ploy, she answer that both '*Gaṇadāsa* and *Haradutta* are excellent in their respective field, since *Gaṇadāsa* is senior in respect to his age so, he must be given the first chance to present over *Haradutta*.' Thus, from the question of the King up to the answer of *Parivrājikā* comes under the *Prayatna* type of *Kāryāvastha*. In the third Act of the play, queen *Irāvati* shows anger at the union of the King and *Mālavikā* and makes a complaint to *Dhāriṇī* regarding that. Consequently, *Mālavikā* and *Bakulābalikā* both are sent behind the bars by *Dhāriṇī*. Moreover, she orders the guard not to release the girls (*Bakulābalikā* and *Mālavikā*) as long as he is not provided with the serpent seal. In such a way an obstacle is created for the king in accomplishing his aim. But in the fourth Act, a concocted story of *Vidūṣaka*'s serpent-bite could fetch the serpent seal from *Dhāriṇī*'s hand. Thus, by the use of that serpent-seal *Vidūṣaka* was able to release *Bakulābalikā* and *Mālavikā*. So, the sheer effort of *Vidūṣaka* resulted in the union of the *Mālavikā* and *Agnimitra*. Here, this circumstance is an example of the *Prāptyāśā* type of *Kāryāvastha*. In the fifth Act of the play, the blooming *Aśoka* tree, and the unfolding of the real identity of *Mālavikā* as the younger sister of *Mādhavasena* are the instances of *Niyatāpti* *Kāryāvastha*. Towards the end of the fifth Act of the play '*Mālavikāgnimitra*', the hero (*Agnimitra*) and heroine (*Mālavikā*) are united permanently after they tied the pious knot of marriage. The King's ultimate intention of getting *Mālavikā* as a wife is accomplished. At the end part of the final Act, queen *Dhāriṇī* unveils *Mālavikā* and prays *Agnimitra* to accept *Mālavikā* as his wife. Consequently, *Agnimitra* accepts *Mālavikā* as his wedded wife. This scene is the example of *Phalāgama* *Kāryāvastha*.

Dialogues play a crucial part in the development of a dramatic storyline because they are the fundamental stage of performing. This is a kind of *Nāṭyokti* or *Nāṭyadharmā*. From an Indian perspective, dramatic speeches are classified into four categories: *Akāśavāṣita* (Aerial speech), *Ātmagata* (Soliloquy), *Apavārīta* (Concealed speaking), and *Janāntika* (Private personal feelings, aside). In the play *Mālavikāgnimitra*, the use of *Svagata* is very much evident. In the first Act of the play, *Gaṇadāsa* praises *Mālavikā* because of her beautiful art of dancing. On his, praise *Bakulābalikā* presents her soliloquy where she mutters to herself that it seems *Mālavikā* may defeat *Irāvati*. Similarly, in the second Act the soliloquy of king *Agnimitra* regarding his thought of *Mālavikā*'s beauty. Moreover, in the third Act *Mālavikā* present her inner thought through her soliloquy, in the fourth Act the description of the incident of monkeys by *Vidūṣaka* bears the example of *Svagata*. The term '*Prakāśa*' denotes something worthy of hearing. There are seven examples of *Prakāśa* in the play *Mālavikāgnimitra*. In the first Act of the play, *Bakulābalikā* made use of '*Prakāśa*' when she said *Gaṇadāsa* that his disciple was a successful dancer because he was satisfied with her. In the same act, *Gaṇadāsa* praised the art of dancing of *Mālavikā*. He added that her dancing skill is even more flourished than him. This is how the information of *Gaṇadāsa* is seen as an example of *Prakāśa*. The quarrel between the two dance masters was also not liked by queen *Dhāriṇī*, and the fulfillment was informed to *Gaṇadāsa* by queen *Dhāriṇī*. Moreover, she made have aware not to fall into the trap of all these unnecessary things. Here, *Dhāriṇī* used *Prakāśa* mode while describing the circumstances. In the 4th act, *Bakulābalikā*'s revelation regarding *Mālavikā*'s jealousy which she does to queen *Irāvati* is also displayed while the king went to meet *Mālavikā* after they were separated for time being. Again here also *Prakāśa* mode of conversation is used. Similarly in other scenes of the play, the example of *Prakāśa* is very much evident. *Janāntika* is a situation where the two characters want to convey their secret message to one another orally amid several characters present on the stage by banding the ring finger and keeping the rest of the fingers in a linear position close to the mouth. In the play, *Mālavikāgnimitra* *Janāntika* is used eleven times. In the 2nd Act of the play, *Gaṇadāsa* being elder to *Haradatta* got the first chance to show the dance presentation on seeking permission from *Agnimitra*,

Gaṇadāsa enters the stage to perform *Śarmiṣṭhā*'s composition of four parts and sung in the medium time. However, the king urged to see *Mālavikā* who was standing behind the curtains. Thus, the king says to *Vidūṣaka* from behind the stage that he wants the curtains to be removed to behold *Mālavikā* as soon as possible. This Private personal feeling of King *Agnimitra* is express to *Vidūṣaka* with the *Janāntika* mode of conversation. In the next narration from the private conversation, *Vidūṣaka* informs the King that *Mālavikā* looks more beautiful than her portrait. However, the king replies that the painter could not appropriately draw her picture perhaps because, in reality, she (*Mālavikā*) is more beautiful than her portrait. Moreover, the private personal feelings and the discussion between *Vidūṣaka* and *Agnimitra* regarding her (*Mālavikā*'s) dance performance before and after her presentation is set in *Janāntika* mode. In the same fashion, in the 4th act, the description of *Agnimitra*'s beautiful palace and the secret conversation of *Jyotsnikā* and *Madanikā* are made in the *Janāntika* mode of *Nāṭyokti*. However, along with the above instances, a few more examples of *Janāntika* are also evident in the play. *Apabārīta* refers to a situation where the character present on the stage conveys a secret message to the other character through whispering and turning his or her back aside on the stage. In the play, *Mālavikāgnimitra Apabārīta* is used six-times. In the first Act of the play, when queen *Dhāriṇī*, *Agnimitra*, and *Vidūṣaka* were going to see the dance competition, then seeing *Agnimitra* in an impatient state, *Vidūṣaka* said 'my friend walk slowly. *Dhāriṇī* may create a disturbance.' The king answered that 'although I'm not in a hurry, still the sound of the drum signifies the completion of my inner desires and which extremely excites me. Similarly, in the 2nd Act when *Agnimitra* becomes impatience after seeing *Mālavikā*, *Vidūṣaka* tells to king from the back of the scene that his beloved (*Mālavikā*) is present before him. So he (*Agnimitra*) can look at her to his heart's content. In the 3rd Act of the play, the king was bewildered at seeing *Irāvati* at *Pramadavana* because *Mālavikā* was also present over there. Both of them i.e. the king and *Mālavikā* were engrossed in their secret meeting. To manage such a queer circumstance, the king took permission from *Vidūṣaka* secretly. This scene is an example of the *Apabārīta* mode of conversation. Apart from that, the use of *Apabārīta* is visible in other scenes of the play as well. Speech behind the curtain signifies that a character without appearing physically on the stage will announce the arrival of something. In the play, *Mālavikāgnimitra* author used the speech from behind the curtain in several scenes. In the 2nd Act of the play, *Vaitālika* announces the midday with a proper description to the king. Similarly, in the 4th act, the incident of the Golden *Aśoka* tree and fulfilment before five nights is another example of *Nepathyokti*. Moreover, at the beginning of the 5th Act, after the *Praveśaka*, two *Vaitālika* described the beauty of the kingdom of king *Agnimitra*. When two characters speak regarding a secret matter to one another in the ear, is called *Karṇa Evaṃ Evaṃ*. Playwright *Kālidāsa* used this feature gratefully in his drama and amazed his audience. In the 1st Act of the play, *Vidūṣaka* and the king discussed the physical and facial beauty of *Mālavikā*. *Vidūṣaka* spoke in *Agnimitra*'s ear secretly. Whereas, at the starting of the 4th Act, *Mālavikā* and *Bakulāvalikā* were sent behind the bars by *Dhāriṇī*. So, to release both, King asked *Vidūṣaka* to find out some ways through which *Mālavikā* and *Bakulāvalikā* could be released. Thus, *Vidūṣaka* found out about a situation he whispered to King's ear. Towards the end of the 4th Act, queen *Irāvati* got to know about the rescue of the serpent seal and the story of the sea pavilion of *Vidūṣaka* from the jailor called *Mādhavikā*. The entire incident was narrated in *Irāvati*'s ear by *Nipuṇikā*. Similarly, in this very fact, the discussion regarding *Mālavikā*'s release from the jail is very much evident in this Act. Here, *Vidūṣaka* says in the ear of the king *Agnimitra*. He utters, 'someone is listening to our discussion let me whisper in your ear.' This is how *Kālidāsa* used the very excellent way the *Karṇa Evaṃ Evaṃ* mode of conversation in four scenes of different acts. According to the *Swapnāyitam* type of *Nāṭyokti*, it is believed that a character will speak while sleeping and reveal certain secrets. In *Kālidāsa*'s *Mālavikāgnimitra*, we get examples of *Nāṭyokti* named *Swapnāyitam*. In the 4th Act, *Vidūṣaka* fell asleep in the sea pavilion while *Mālavikā* and *Agnimitra* were busy talking with one another.

As per the rules of the Indian Dramaturgy, the dramatic performance would end with a benedictory stanza called *Prasasti* or more popularly known as "Bharatavākya" in the same way as it begins with a

benedictory stanza called 'Nandi'. According to the prevailing system, the *prasasti* contains an expression of good wishes from the participants and the words of good wishes or blessings are uttered by the character of virtues or spiritual merits. Following these principles of dramaturgy in *kālidāsa* playwrights have introduced *Prasasti* or *Bharatavākya* into their plays as a sign of completion of performance. In the play, *Mālavikāgnimitra*'s blessings have been sought from God to make the king able to dispel the calamities of the subject.

The appropriate classification of the *Mālavikāgnimitra* could be a point of contention, whether it is technically a *Nāṭaka* or a *Nāṭikā*. This is clear that the *Mālavikāgnimitra* provides answers to all of *Bharata*'s definitions of *Nāṭikā*. There are only two places where it might deviate from the description. Firstly, the plot is stated to be similar to a *Prakaraṇa*, indicating that it must be invented by the author. This play's plot is based on historical events and characters, and it does not fall under the *Utpādyā* category. Second, *Nāṭikā* is the fourth act, while *Mālavikāgnimitra* is a five-act play. Because the plot is based on historical characters, it cannot be considered entirely the poet's invention. However, the plot's fundamental elements, such as the king's love for the maid *Mālavikā* and the palace intrigues are most likely the author's creations. The historical figures serve as a peg on which the king's romance is hung. As a result, the plot can be considered to fit *Nāṭikā*'s criteria in spirit, if not technically in form. In contrast, *Bharata*'s definition of a *Nāṭaka* is remarkable; most of these classifications are not directly applicable in this play. There is no reason why the *Mālavikāgnimitra* should not be included among the *Nāṭakas* if the letter of the law is observed. Additional proof for this could be found in the play's *Prastāvanā*, where the term *Nāṭaka* is mentioned. The play's atmosphere and general mood are more related to a *Nāṭikā* than a *Nāṭaka*.

The theme of *Kālidāsa*'s *Mālavikāgnimitra* exemplifies the unity of time, place, and action. The plot revolves entirely around *Agnimitra*'s royal dwelling, the palace, and its surroundings. The first act takes place in a singing hall near the palace, and *Bakulāvalikā* goes on a visit to *Gaṇadāsa*, who informs them that he is taking a short break after teaching *Mālavikā* the *Pañcāṅgābhinaya*. Thereafter, the scene shifts to the palace's court. The second act is a continuation of the first, with the action taking place in the presentation hall, which is also located nearby the palace. The third act takes place in the royal garden near the palace, and according to *Parabhṛtikā*'s statements, *Mālavikā* has been grumpy for a few days. The fourth Act is situated in the palace, where the king receives word from *Vidūṣaka* that *Mālavikā* has been imprisoned by Queen *Dhāriṇī* at *Irāvati*'s request. The fifth act's *Praveśaka* depicts a location near *Antahpura*, and queen *Dhāriṇī* is excited to see the blooming *Aśoka* with the king. As a result, the *Mālavikāgnimitra* well conveys a sense of place by representing the royal garden, *Samudragṛha*, *Antahpura*, and the court itself, all of which are close to the palace. All scenes in the play are set inside or take place in the King's Court hall. In Act II, all of the characters are transported to the palace's theatre. The *Pramadavana* and the *Samudragṛha*, respectively, are the settings for Acts III and IV. In the *Pramadavana*, Act V is re-enacted. In the *Pramadavana*, Act V is re-enacted. Location changes, therefore, do not pose a significant challenge to those wishing to present the drama. The continuous action of rivalry and so on helps to maintain the unity of action. Though the Greek system proposed the unity of time, i.e., the incidents may be displayed as occurring in one single time, it is free of lag and in continuity. The plot is never the driving force behind emotional realism. In this fashion, the plot closely resembles the three unities' laws to a large extent.

Mālavikā and *Agnimitra* are the protagonists and heroines in *Mālavikāgnimitra*. *Mālavikā* arrives in Act IV as an unknown yet gorgeous and skillful dancer. When *Agnimitra* sees her, he falls head over heels in love with her. *Agnimitra* hears the word of *Vīrasena* of *Vidarbha*'s victory and *Mādhavasena*'s release in Act V. The conquering country sends gifts, including two young female artists. The heroine performs a dance with perfect *sausṭhava* and posture in Act II, and her dance composition is called *catuṣpadā chalika* with a medium tempo. *Chalika* was a form of dance in which the dancer communicated her emotions while pretending to be someone else. To represent her love-lorn state before the union, the heroine employs the *śuca* and *śakha* method of four-fold *abhinaya*.

Conclusion:

When we begin and continue with the relevant research, the numerous issues and disagreements of the related studies will undoubtedly be highly informative, while also dispelling some previous misunderstandings or misinterpretations. As a result, in any form of art, such points are conceiving huge gems of various valid facts that assist us in rewriting history.

Of course, certain elements of *Kālidāsa's* play did not comply with dramaturgy canons in their entirety. It has become evident that the dramatist is truly remarkable in terms of literary inventiveness. As a result, a dramatist of *Kālidāsa's* brilliance cannot be expected to have any ability to accommodate the canons of dramaturgy in his works. His disobedience to dramaturgy could be because dramaturgical canons emerged after *Kālidāsa's* literary activity. The reason for this could be that dramaturgical theories had not yet gained widespread acceptance during *Kālidāsa's* writing career.

As a result of the foregoing debate, we can conclude that *Kālidāsa's Mālavikāgnimitra Nāṭaka* is a perfect *Nāṭaka* variety of drama that follows all of the norms and regulations of Sanskrit dramaturgy, and as a result, it has a special place in the hearts of Sanskrit lovers and others.

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